

Impact of Withdrawal from Chronic Nicotine on Strategy Set-shifting in C57BL/6J Mice

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Abstract

Nicotine is a major psychoactive and addictive component of tobacco. Although cessation of tobacco use produces various somatic and affective signs of withdrawal during the first few days of abstinence, withdrawal-related cognitive deficits are considered to be the most critical symptoms that predict relapse. The present study was designed to examine the effects of precipitated nicotine withdrawal on cognitive control processes. We employed a mouse operant cognitive flexibility task that required the animals to shift attention from a visual cue to a spatial cue. Male C57BL/6J were implanted with subcutaneous osmotic minipumps to deliver either saline or nicotine (18mg/kg/day; base) for 4 weeks. Precipitated withdrawal was induced via a subcutaneous injection of mecamylamine, a non-specific nicotinic receptor antagonist (3 mg/kg), 20minutes before testing during the fourth week. Mice undergoing precipitated nicotine withdrawal required higher number of trials to attain criterion as compared to their respective controls. Error analysis indicated that impaired performance following nicotine withdrawal was mostly related to the animals' inability to maintain a new learning strategy rather than increased perseveration to the previously acquired strategy. Interestingly, mecamylamine treatment *per se* also disrupted this form of cognitive flexibility and these impairments were associated with higher perseverative errors. These findings suggest that the ability to sustain cognitive control is disrupted during nicotine abstinence, which may lead to relapse.

1. Introduction

Nicotine is a powerful addictive and psychoactive compound in tobacco, whose exposure causes characteristic cognitive-behavioral effects (Swan & Lessov-Schlaggar, 2007). Tobacco smoking is initially taken as a voluntary action that evolves into an addiction. Since smoking is a

global health issue and rates of relapse among those attempting to quit are high, it is necessary to further our understanding of how nicotine affects cognition and develop more effective treatments. Cessation therapies assist smokers' attempts to quit, though they are only marginally successful (Ranney, Melvin, Lux, McClain, & Lohr, 2006). For this reason, studying the neurobiology of nicotine addiction is a useful goal.

Neural circuits of addiction and cognition intersect and the circuitry of the latter can influence drug use (and vice versa). In particular, frontostriatal circuitry modulates executive functions like decision-making processes and cognitive control. Impairments to these circuits may cause compulsive drug use and the loss of cognitive control, which characteristic of addiction (Galvan et al., 2005). In drug addicts, cognitive deficits take the form of an inability to switch responses to stimuli that were associated with the drug stimulus or reward (Garavan & Stout, 2005). The ability to switch one's behavioral response in different contexts is called *cognitive flexibility* and it considered a major element of executive functioning. Since human studies have revealed that executive functions like cognitive flexibility are impaired in drug addicts, this current study assesses cognitive flexibility in our nicotine-treated animals.

This present study assesses the effects of precipitated withdrawal from chronic nicotine while mice undergo an extradimensional shift within an operant conditioning paradigm. We hypothesized that our mice would experience impairments in their extradimensional shifting. An extradimensional shift requires subjects to switch strategies between dimensions; in this case, animals were required to attend to a visual cue first and then a spatial location contingent to the reward. Previously, it has been reported that a high dose of chronic nicotine did not affect set-shifting learning (part of the extradimensional shift) (Ortega, Tracy, Gould, & Parikh, 2013). Chronic nicotine or saline was administered via subcutaneously implanted mini-osmotic pumps.

Additionally, brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) levels in the dorsal striatum were quantified since BDNF is integral to learning, LTP in corticostriatal projections, and nicotine addiction (Staiger, 2002) (Potter & Newhouse, 2008) (Zhang et al., 2010).

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Subjects

Male C57BL/6J mice (PND 42-56) were purchased from Jackson Laboratories (Bar Harbor, ME). Animals were individually housed in a temperature/humidity-controlled environment with a 12-h light/dark cycle (07:00 lights on). Mice began progressive water-restriction (from 4 hours daily to 5 min of water) beginning one week before the commencement of the training schedule. Initial body mass ranged from 20–25 g prior to water restriction and operant training. Mice underwent behavioral training 7 days/week between 9:00 and 16:00 h and received 5 min of water at the end of daily operant sessions in addition to the saccharin-sweetened water received as a reward for correct operant responses. Food pellets (PMI LabDiet) were available *ad libitum* during the experiment. These experimental measures were authorized by the Institutional Care and Use Committee (IACUC) of Temple University and complied with regulations from the National Institute of Health.

2.2. Mouse operant cognitive flexibility task

This current study investigates cognitive flexibility using an operant conditioning paradigm. The task provides a means to study the cognitive deficits accrued from precipitated nicotine withdrawal. Our automated operant task, which is analogous to the cross-maze task and the WCST, is capable of measuring both extradimensional shifts (visual discrimination to set-shifting) and intradimensional shifts (set-shifting to reversal learning), though this study is

concerned with extradimensional shifts only. Correct cue responses were rewarded by saccharin-sweetened water and incorrect responses were punished by a 10 second extinguishment of the houselight. With respect to this negative feedback, our task resembles the Wisconsin Card Sorting Task used to study human cognition (Buchsbaum, Greer, Chang, & Berman, 2005).

2.2.1. Apparatus

Tasks were learned and assessed in classic mouse modular operant chambers (interior dimensions: 15.9 cm L × 14.0 cm W × 12.7 cm H; MED Associates; St. Albans, VT). Chambers contained a standard grid floors, houselights (28 V DC, 100 mA), and panels each with two large cue lights inset (2.5 cm; 28 V DC, 100 mA). A centralized reward port was located between the two cue lights from which a 10 μ L cup was offered after a correct responses. The cup was attached to a fluid dipper that carried water into the chamber. The operant chambers also contained two ultra-sensitive retractable levers (ENV-312-2M). Operant chambers were situated in sound-attenuating PVC cubicles; an exhaust fan (28 V DC) inside each chamber ventilated the area and provided low-level background noise. All automated actions, including visual cue presentations, lever operations, and reward deliveries were programmed in Medstate notation via MED-PC IV software (distributed by Med Associates) on a PC (Dell OptiPlex™ 960). Program commands were relayed from the PC to the 8 input/16 output SmrtCtrl™ interface, which controlled the operant chambers.

2.2.2. Autoshaping

An FR-1 reinforcement schedule was used to aid mice in acquiring the lever press response and for subsequent reinforcement (rewarded with 10 μ L of .066% saccharin solution). Both the left and right levers were protracted for the entire 30 minute session. In addition,

noncontingent reinforcers were provided every minute to strengthen the association between the dipper's activation and the reward's presence. Lever presses on the dominant lever (i.e., the lever with 5 more presses than the other lever) were not reinforced until lever presses were balanced. Animals were considered to have learned the task by meeting a standard criterion – earn at least 30 rewards during one 30 minute session. Successful performers advanced to the pretraining phase.

2.2.3. Pretraining

Illumination of the houselight signaled the beginning of each pretraining session. Either the left or right lever was presented and remained extended for 10 s or until the subject pressed the lever. Lever presses within the 10 s window were rewarded with saccharin solution. Failures to lever press were deemed *omissions* and resulted in a resetting of the ITI. To prevent more than 5 activations of the lever on the same side, lever presentations were pseudorandomized. Moreover, a light cue above the extended lever was lit in 50% of the trials to prevent a novelty effect in the later *visual discrimination* phase. Animals were considered to have learned the task after meeting the task criterion – earn 30 rewards with less than 20% omissions for three consecutive days.

2.2.4. Visual Discrimination

The visual discrimination phase also began with the illumination of the houselight and included 30 trials (ITI of 9 ± 3 s). In each trial, animals had 2 s to observe a visual cue (left or right cue light) followed by subsequent 5 s presentation of both levers while the light cue remained illuminated. Light cues, which were pseudorandomized throughout the session, and levers presentations co-terminated. Lever presses on the side with the cue light lit were deemed

correct, whereas lever presses on the lever opposite the activated panel were considered incorrect. Correct responses were rewarded with saccharin solution and incorrect responses were punished with a 10 s “time out” period during which the houselight was extinguished. The houselight was illuminated after punishment and the ITI was reinstated. Trials during which no levers responses occurred were classified as omitted trials. Mice were trained on this phase for 8 days and advanced to strategy set-shifting afterward.

2.2.5. *Strategy set-shifting*

General experimental procedures in *strategy set-shifting* are similar to other phases. However, this phase requires animals to learn an egocentric lever response strategy to earn rewards (Figure 1). This phase follows visual discrimination and requires animals to undergo an extradimensional strategy shift from a visual cue to an egocentric lever response. Mice were taught to lever press either the left or the right lever, irrespective of the presentation of the light cue above the levers. For example, if the animal was randomly assigned to the set-shifting phase (right side), correct responses were those in which the animal pressed the right lever. Left lever presses were considered incorrect and resulted in a punishment phase of 10 s during the houselight was extinguished. Half the animals were assigned to the set-shifting (left side) phase for which the opposite was the case. Following 8 days on strategy set-shifting, animals were sacrificed for the collection of brain tissue for a BDNF ELISA analyses.

2.2.6. *Behavioral measures*

Behavioral measures were recorded during each session. Measures include the number of correct responses, incorrect responses (errors), omissions, and response latencies, perseverative errors, and learning errors. Response accuracy was computed for all sessions – correct responses/

(correct + incorrect responses) \times 100. Further, total trials up to and including criterion, errors to criterion, and omissions were calculated. Statistical analysis was conducted using independent sample t-tests and p values $\leq .05$ were considered significant.

Somatic signs were recorded for all animals during the first and second days on strategy-set-shifting. Animals were scored for symptoms of nicotine withdrawal 20 minutes following saline/mecamylamine challenge in a quiet room. Paw tremors, retropulsion, piloerection, head shakes, backing, and scratching were tallied live for 20 minutes by two scorers. Behavioral scoring was immediately followed by operant conditioning.

2.3 Experimental design and nicotine withdrawal

On the day that pretraining criteria were met, mice were randomly assigned to one of four conditions (nicotine-saline, nicotine-mecamylamine, saline-saline, or saline-mecamylamine) and subcutaneously implanted with a mini-osmotic pump. These pumps (model 1004; DURECT Corporation, Cupertino, CA) administered 0.11 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$ of drug solutions for 28 days. Drug solutions were either 100 μL of sterile saline or nicotine hydrogen tartrate (Sigma Co., St Louis, MO, USA) dissolved in saline. Surgeries were performed on isoflurane-anesthetized mice in an aseptic environment; pumps administered 18 mg/kg/day of nicotine (reported as free base). This dose yields plasma cotinine levels similar to highly dependent chronic smokers (100-150 ng/mL in our nicotine-treated mice).

Nicotine-saline mice received a nicotine pump and saline injections during set-shifting. Nicotine-mecamylamine mice received a nicotine pump and were injected with the drug mecamylamine, which is a non-specific nicotinic receptor antagonist. Saline-saline mice received a saline pump and saline injections. Saline-mecamylamine mice were implanted with a saline

pump and received mecamlamine injections. All acute administration of either saline or mecamlamine occurred during the strategy set-shift to mimic control or withdrawal conditions.

Mice were given *ad libitum* water and 48 hours of recovery time following surgery.

Pretraining was continued for 9 additional days after animals recovered to assess their cognition.

To prevent overlearning, mice were given two additional days off the task for every day during which they omitted 20% or fewer pretraining trials (Figure 2).

Nicotine-mecamlamine mice were injected with the drug mecamlamine subcutaneously before performing on the first set-shifting day. After scoring somatic signs for withdrawal, nicotine-mecamlamine mice were trained on the set-shifting task. Although somatic signs were only recorded for the first two days for these animals, mecamlamine injections were given on all 8 days of the phase (Figure 2). Nicotine-saline mice received the same dose of nicotine and the same behavioral training, but with saline injections during set-shifting. Saline-mecamlamine mice were injected with mecamlamine to control for the effects of nicotine. Saline-saline mice served as a baseline for all groups and they received chronic saline through osmotic pumps and via injections. Following the final day on set-shifting, mice were sacrificed and their brain tissues were collected for ELISA assays (Figure 2).

2.4. BDNF ELISA

Brains were dissected to extract the dorsal striatum. Striatal tissues were taken from both hemispheres and pooled. All brain samples were homogenized using a glass tissue pulverizer in 1 mL of ice-cold buffer (50 mM HEPES NaOH, pH 7.4, 0.32 M sucrose, 5 mM MgCl₂, 0.2 mM EDTA, 0.2 mM EGTA, 1% Triton X-100 and protease inhibitor cocktail). Homogenates were stored on ice for 30 min and centrifuged for 15 min at 13,000 g to precipitate tissue lysates.

Pellets and supernatants were separated and stored at -80 °C. Protein concentrations were

computed using a modified Lowry Protein Assay (Pierce, Rockford, IL). Afterward, a mouse BDNF ELISA kit (IBL-America, Minneapolis, MN) was used to quantify BDNF levels in the dorsal striatum. Lysates were analyzed in duplicates and data are expressed as pg/mg protein.

3. Results

Visual Discrimination Learning

We compared nicotine's effects on visual discrimination in relation to saline's effects. Nicotine treated animals performed fewer trials to criterion (124.92, 5.89) as compared to saline controls (150.81, 11.65) ($t(27) = 1.85, p = .076$). Nicotine-treated animals' omissions (6.923, 1.77) were comparable to the saline-treated mice (4.125, 1.48) ($t(27) = 1.22, p = .232$). As well, the nicotine-treated animals committed fewer *errors* to reach criterion (25.77, 2.66) than did the saline-treated animals (34.06, 4.61) ($t(27) = 1.47, p = .154$.)

Strategy Set-Shifting Learning

Strategy set-shifting (following visual discrimination) performed trials to criteria were analyzed. Saline-mecamylamine animals (172.88, 9.92) required more trials to reach criterion compared to saline-saline animals (143.25, 6.44) ($t(14) = 2.504, p = .025$). Compared to saline-saline mice, nicotine-saline mice (156.75, 9.52) ($t(14) = 1.174, p = .260$) required about the same number of trials to reach criterion (~~$t(14) = 2.395, p = .024$~~). There was a trend for nicotine-mecamylamine mice, who required more performed trials to reach criteria than saline-saline animals (161.67, 6.62) ($t(15) = 1.983, p = .066$)

Saline-mecamylamine mice (26.5, 3.11) committed more perseverative errors compared to saline controls (19.38, 2.37) ($t(14) = 1.823, p = .090$), although this was not significant.

Nicotine-saline (22.88, 2.56) ($t(14) = 1.004, p=.332$) and nicotine-mecamylamine mice (18.00, 2.33) ($t(15) = .413, p=.685$) did not ^{differs} significantly more often than saline controls.

Learning errors, a combination of regressive errors and never-reinforced errors, were analyzed too. Compared to saline controls (13.88, 4.06), saline-mecamylamine mice (10.38, 2.82) did not commit more learning errors ($t(14) = .708, p=.490$). Nicotine-saline mice (12.75, 1.96) ($t(14) = .250, p=.806$) and nicotine-mecamylamine mice (13.89, 2.01) ($t(15) = .003, p=.998$) also did not have significantly higher learning errors with regard to saline controls.

With respect to omissions, saline-mecamylamine mice (33.38, 8.10) committed significantly more omissions than the saline-saline mice (6.75, 2.26) ($t(14) = 3.168, p=.007$). Nicotine-saline mice (9.13, 2.36) did not omit significantly more trials than saline-saline mice ($t(14) = .728, p=.479$). Nicotine-mecamylamine mice (19.56, 3.51) showed a trend to omitting more trials than saline-saline mice ($t(15) = 2.078, p=.055$).

Saline-mecamylamine mice (1.142s, .062s), when lever pressing correctly, had significantly shorter latencies (see Figure 3) compared to saline-saline mice (.837s, .078s) ($t(14) = 3.053, p=.009$). Nicotine-saline mice (.788s, .025s) did not have significantly different correct latencies with regard to saline-saline mice ($t(14) = .600, p=.558$), although nicotine-mecamylamine mice (1.12s, .071s) did lever press significantly slower compared to saline-saline mice ($t(15) = .269, p=.017$). When animals lever pressed incorrectly, latencies for saline-mecamylamine mice (1.57s, .135s) were significantly longer compared to saline-saline controls ($t(14) = 2.407, p=.030$). Compared to controls, nicotine-saline mice (.848s, .135s) did not have significantly different incorrect latencies ($t(14) = 1.279, p=.222$), whereas nicotine-mecamylamine mice (1.56s, .165s) were trending towards significantly longer latencies ($t(15) = 2.094, p=.054$).

Altered Striatal BDNF levels following precipitated withdrawal from Chronic Nicotine

Compared to saline-saline controls, saline-mecamylamine mice did not experience significantly higher striatal BDNF levels (14.41%, 9.66%) ($t(15) = 1.187$, $p = .254$) (Figure 4). Nicotine-saline mice, however, did have significantly suppressed striatal BDNF levels (23.89%, 5.05%) ($t(13) = 2.730$, $p = .017$). When compared to controls, nicotine-mecamylamine BDNF levels were not significantly higher (13.75%, 15.65%) ($t(15) = .769$, $p = .454$).

4. Discussion

Mecamylamine-precipitated withdrawal from chronic nicotine impaired strategy set-shifting by damaging animals' ability to maintain the learning of a new egocentric response strategy (higher regressive errors) rather than promoting perseveration to the previously acquired strategy. Interestingly, mecamylamine treatment as such caused more perseverative errors, an indication of impaired cognitive flexibility and decreased inhibition of prepotent responses (among saline-mecamylamine mice). Mecamylamine challenges also drove reaction times and the frequency of omissions higher during set-shifting. Learning deficits in the saline-mecamylamine mice suggest that nicotine receptors are required for extradimensional set-shifting and cognitive control. These data implicate nicotinic receptors in decision-making processes that are also influenced by motivational and attentional mechanisms.

Previous experiments have reported that withdrawal results in significantly higher BDNF levels in the striatum, which may manifest as deficits in cognitive flexibility (Yeom, Shim, Lee, & Hahn, 2005). Likewise, we found 15% more BDNF in the striatum in mice undergoing precipitated withdrawal – nicotine-mecamylamine and saline-mecamylamine mice (Figure 4).

Our BDNF ELISA analysis also found significantly reduced BDNF levels (30% less compared to controls) in the striatum in nicotine-saline animals.

A potentially limiting factor is the means by which nicotine withdrawal was induced. Although modeling nicotine withdrawal via a nAChR antagonist produces robust withdrawal symptoms, it does not simulate actual spontaneous nicotine cessation. Unlike spontaneous withdrawal, nicotine remains in the animal's system during precipitated withdrawal, allowing it to continually bind to unused nAChRs. This may explain our failure to discover increased BDNF in the striatal regions of precipitated withdrawal animals. To further examine the effects of nicotine withdrawal on cognitive functions, a spontaneous withdrawal design may be a valuable course of research.

Globally, our present results suggest that relapse during nicotine withdrawal may be influenced by loss of cognitive functions like inhibition and cognitive control. Moreover, nicotinic receptors are required for cognitive flexibility and through desensitization and upregulation during nicotine usage, lead to these cognitive deficits (Granon, Faure, & Changeux, 2003).

Appendix

Figure 1 – Extradimensional Set-Shifting Test

This figure outlines the strategies required by mice to perform visual discrimination and strategy set-shifting correctly.

Figure 2 – Behavioral Training Schedule

This bar diagram represents the schedule of behavioral training and drug manipulations animals underwent.

Figure 3 – Response Latencies during Strategy Set-Shifting

Figure 4 – Striatal BDNF Levels Following Operant Training

IMPACT OF WITHDRAWAL

Acknowledgments

I would like to thank Rachel Poole for assisting with surgeries, dissections, and data analysis. Robert Cole was instrumental in conducting Lowry and ELISA assays, performing statistical tests, and reviewing drafts of this paper. I also thank Sean Naughton, Dawn Guzman, and Leonardo Ortega for assisting with behavioral training, protein assays, and other technical assistance. I have greatly benefited from Thomas Gould, who designed this study.

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